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A preliminary investigation into sandwich structures made of aluminium skins and gaped-bamboo ring core

F. Napolitano^{(a), *}, J.C. dos Santos^(b), R.J. da Silva^(c), G.G. Braga^(d), R.T.S. Freire^(e),
L.A. de Oliveira^(f), TH Panzera^(g)

(a) 0000-0001-6368-1534 (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(b) 0000-0002-7485-491X (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(c) 0000-0001-8016-3165 (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(d) 0000-0002-9027-8211 (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(e) 0000-0001-5206-5939 (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(f) 0000-0001-8214-673X (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(g) 0000-0001-7091-456X (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

* Corresponding author: flavio_napolitano@ufsj.edu.br

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Abstract: Sandwich panels have been used for sporting goods to aerospace components. The new guidelines in engineering designs, whenever possible, have driven towards sustainable and biodegradable materials, minimising disposal costs and environmental impact. This work describes the physical and mechanical properties of sandwich panels made of aluminium skins, circular honeycomb core with bamboo rings and castor-biobased adhesive. Bamboo rings are placed side by side with a gap in order to make the panels lighter, aiming to obtain higher specific mechanical properties and reduce manufacturing costs.

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1. Introduction

The demand for sustainable and recyclable materials in engineering projects has risen worldwide, mainly with a focus on minimising environmental impacts. Composite sandwich panels with low-density core material have high specific flexural stiffness, strength and favourable compressive behaviour as structural characteristics. These features make them suitable for aerospace, sports, automotive and other applications [1]. A variety of materials have been developed and evaluated as sandwich cores, the most common being hexagonal alveolar cells made of aluminium and stainless steel [2]. Some research [3–9] has shown the advantages of using tubular honeycombs to

improve the mechanical performance of panels. This work describes an eco-friendly sandwich panel composed of aluminium skins, bamboo ring core and biobased adhesive. Bamboo rings are placed side by side in a hexagonal packing with and without gaps. Gaps are inserted to reduce panel density and enhance specific mechanical properties, as well as reducing manufacturing costs.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials and Manufacturing

The sandwich panels are produced by a hand-made process. The materials are made with aluminium sheets (type ISO 2024 with 0.4 mm thick) as skins and bamboo rings as the core. Bamboo rings (*Bambusa tuldooides*) are obtained at the Federal University of São João del-Rei (CSA-Brazil). Based on previous work, bamboo rings with a diameter of 30 ± 2 mm are selected [9, 10]. An abrasive diamond saw is used to cut the bamboo rings with 14 ± 2 mm in height. The rings are placed following a hexagonal packing, adding a 15 mm gap between them, corresponding to their radius, and without gaps (in contact). Bamboo rings are bonded to the upper and lower aluminium skins with an adhesive thickness of 1.5 mm. The adhesive is a thermosetting polymer based on a castor oil polyurethane system sourced by *Imperveg*[®] (Brazil). The bonding process is carried out at 25°C and $55\pm 5\%$ humidity. Sandwich panels are produced with dimensions of 240 x 90 x 15 mm³ in accordance with ASTM C393.

2.2. Mechanical and physical tests

Mechanical properties are obtained through a three-point bending test following ASTM C393. A speed test of 6 mm/min and a span length of 150 mm is considered (Figure 1a). An Instron testing machine equipped with a 50 kN load cell is used. Two core arrangements are investigated, without gaps (Figure 1b) and with gaps (Figure 1c) under a hexagonal packing distribution. Three replicates are produced for each experimental condition. The panels are weighed and measured (using a digital calliper) to obtain their equivalent density dividing mass per volume.

Fig. 1. Three-point bending (a), hexagonal core packing arrangement without gaps (b) and (c) with gaps.

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1 describes the physical and mechanical properties of the sandwich composites produced. Panels with gaps between bamboo rings increase 90% of empty voids, leading to a 20% reduction in equivalent density over

the hexagonal core packing arrangement without gaps. The incorporation of gaps reduces the mechanical properties of the panels significantly. There is a 63% reduction in mean maximum load and ultimate stress. However, the small size of the samples may contribute to this behaviour, as reported by Silva et al. [11]. In other words, deformation is predominant in the core, as the dimensions of the specimen are smaller (ratio between panel width and panel thickness $\ll 20$). As the gaps between bamboo rings tend to reduce the core rigidity, the mechanical properties of the panels are expected to decrease, particularly if the loading configuration leads to more deformation of the core. This consideration is demonstrated by the greater deformation suffered by the panels made with gaps between bamboo rings, i.e., there is an increase of 125% in the mean ultimate strain. Moreover, the slope of the straight-line portion of the mean bending stress-strain curve of rigid core panels with small dimensions is closer to the overall flexural modulus of the core [11]. In this way, incorporating gaps tend to reduce core flexural modulus by 84%.

The load versus displacement curves are shown in Figure 2a. The primary fracture mode is debonding (blue arrows in Figure 2b and Figure 2c), due to the occurrence of skin dimpling (yellow circles in Figure 2b and Figure 2c). There are also cracks in bamboo ring at the edges close to the local vicinity of the indenter (Figure 2d). The latter probably occurs due to the transverse shear load generated by the compressive (F_c) and tensile stresses (F_t) in the upper and lower skins, respectively. The debonding failure mode also indicates a smaller skin-to-core adhesive contact area by the absence of rings. It is noteworthy that the reduction of equivalent density with the introduction of gaps does not compensate in terms of mechanical properties, since the specific properties of panels with gaps are still lower.

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties of the sandwich structures.

Panel Properties	Without gaps	With gaps	Gap effect (%)
Empty voids (mm ²)	7035	13397	+ 90%
Equivalent density (g/cm ³)	0.500 ± 0.014	0.400 ± 0.005	- 20%
Maximum load (N)	1931 ± 40	719 ± 95	- 63%
Mean ultimate stress (MPa)	18.68 ± 0.32	7.00 ± 0.87	- 63%
Mean ultimate strain (%)	0.88 ± 0.14	1.98 ± 0.48	+ 125%
Core flexural modulus (GPa)	3.45 ± 0.24	0.56 ± 0.03	- 84%
Panel Specific Properties	Without gaps	With gaps	Gap effect (%)
Maximum load (N.cm ³ /g)	3866 ± 161	1797 ± 218	- 54%
Mean ultimate stress (MPa.cm ³ /g)	37.39 ± 1.45	17.49 ± 1.98	- 53%
Core flexural modulus (GPa.cm ³ /g)	6.91 ± 0.46	1.40 ± 0.08	- 80%

Fig. 2. Bending load versus displacement curves (a); debonding fracture of panels without gaps (b) and with gaps (c); bamboo ring cracks at the edges near the local vicinity of the indenter (d).

4. Conclusions

Percentage reductions of 20%, 63% and 84 % in equivalent density, load-bearing capacity (maximum load and ultimate stress) and core flexural modulus, respectively, were achieved by panels made with gaped bamboo ring cores. This behaviour is probably related to the dimensions of the specimen used in the tests, whose loading configuration provides greater deformations in the core. Investigations of specimens in structural dimensions (with larger span length) should provide less difference between the mechanical properties. Equivalent density reduction did not lead to superior specific properties. Sandwich panels with gaps smaller than 15 mm and larger dimensions will be the scope of future investigations.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRediT author statement

F Napolitano: Conceptualisation; Investigation; Data curation; Validation; Formal analysis; Writing – original draft. **JC Santos:** Conceptualisation; Investigation; Data curation; Validation; Formal analysis; Writing – original draft. **RJ da Silva:** Conceptualisation; Formal analysis; Writing – original draft. **TH Panzera:** Conceptualisation; Methodology; Resources; Supervision; Writing – review. **GG Braga:** Investigation. **RTS Freire:** Writing – review. **LA Oliveira:** Conceptualisation.

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References

- [1] R. Gibson, Principles of Composite Material Mechanics, CRC Press, Boca Raton/ USA, 2007.
- [2] T. Bitzer, Honeycomb Technology, Chapman & Hall, London/UK, 1997.
- [3] T. Gotkhindi, K. Simha, In-plane effective shear modulus of generalized circular honeycomb structures and bundled tubes in a diamond array structure, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 101–102 (2015) 292–308.
- [4] R.K. Oruganti, A.K. Ghosh, FEM analysis of transverse creep in honeycomb structures, *Acta Mater.* 56 (4) (2008) 726–735.
- [5] L.L. Hu, X.L. He, G.P. Wu, T.X. Yu, Dynamic crushing of the circular-celled honeycombs under out-of-plane impact, *Int. J. Impact Eng.* 75 (2015) 150–161.
- [6] T. Lin, T. Chen, J. Huang, In-plane elastic constants and strengths of circular cell honeycombs, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 72 (12) (2012) 1380–1386.
- [7] J. Chung, A. Waas, The in-plane elastic properties of circular cell and elliptical cell honeycombs, *Acta Mech.* 144 (1–2) (2000) 29–42.
- [8] N. Cabrera, B. Alcock, T. Peijs, Design and manufacture of all-PP sandwich panels based on co-extruded polypropylene tapes, *Compos. Part B: Eng.* 39 (7–8) (2008) 1183–1195.
- [9] LA Oliveira, Development and Characterization of Sandwich-Type Structural Composites Containing Aluminum Sheets and Bamboo Rings, Doctoral Thesis, UFSJ, 2021
- [10] Oliveira, P. R., Bonaccorsi, A. M. S., Panzera, T. H., Christoforo, A. L., & Scarpa, F. (2017). Sustainable sandwich composite structures made from aluminium sheets and disposed bottle caps. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 120(April), 38–45. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2017.08.013>).
- [11] R.J. da Silva et al. A core rigidity classifier method and a novel approach to account for geometric effects on the elastic properties of sandwich structures. *Composite Structures*, Volume 282, 2022. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2021.115075>).